

THE IMPACT OF KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT ON ORGANIZATIONAL COMPETITIVENESS (CASE: SAMAN INSURANCE FIRM)

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Abstract

Organizational knowledge is embedded in procedures, individual employees, systems, which shaping the way that the tangible organizational assets and resources are used in order to create competitive advantage for organization. In today's competitive world, productivity affect by different factors and knowledge competitive advantage as influencing factor can benefit firms. The aim of current research is to investigate the role of knowledge management on organizational competitiveness. Finding of research (according to Cocran 196 insurance executives were asked) supported all hypothesis. Finding show that knowledge sharing had significant impact on Tacit and Explicit knowledge. Beside it Knowledge sharing had highest impact on Explicit knowledge of organization.

JEL classification: D83

Keywords: Knowledge Management, Organizational Competitiveness, Tacit knowledge, Explicit Knowledge.

1. INTRODUCTION

Organizational management main objective is to ensure effective and efficient use of its diverse resources such as labor, capital, materials, energy and information in order to achieve competitiveness and to increase productivity. Iranian firms strive to maintain high productivity through competency and dissemination of policies.

Recently, the resourced-based view (RBV) model of competitiveness has emerged (Grant, 2016) supported by theories on the growth of the firm and firm resources. The RBV posits competitiveness to be **based on firms' resources, i.e. whatever a firm owns and uses in production. In addition to owning** resources, another model – the core competence model (Prahalad et al, 1999) posits that firms need to possess core competences -- distinctive, rare, inimitable characteristics a firm requires to be competitive.

In today's rapid technological change, companies are in constant and incessant struggle to maintain competitive advantage through market differentiation by providing superior products and services. Among **various methods, the management in organizations are increasing their focus on employees' know-how,** past experiences and expertise in their quest to excel in achieving their goal. Additionally, improving the communication among employees as well as changing **the organization's culture to a share-what-you- know is integral in todays' organizations.** They could only achieve this by **capturing the employees' know-how** and its dissemination throughout the organization.

Clearly, Knowledge has become an asset, next to labor, land and capital (Sher & Lee, 2004). Even though some forms of intellectual capital are transferable, internal/personal knowledge is not easily articulated, captured, retained, disseminated and reused. In fact, knowledge is a valuable asset that must be managed. The basis of Knowledge management is to fine strategy that the right knowledge with the right shape put in the right people. (Milton et al, 1999). This research demonstrates organizational success as a by-product of the critical success factors of implementing Knowledge management. Organizational knowledge is embedded in processes, procedures, individual employees, systems, and also culture which shaping the

way that the tangible organizational assets and resources are used in order to create value for the firm. In today's competitive world, productivity as a philosophy which is based on improvement strategy, forms the most important aim of any organization; therefore, knowledge management promises to create the proper structure and the necessary technological infrastructure in organization and human-driven placement. In addition, using employee's share knowledge can help organizations to achieve their goals as knowledge based organization (Ghasemi, 2001). The aim of current research is to investigate the role of knowledge management on organizational competency.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT

Knowledge resides in the **individual's brain and only when it is articulated and/or captured becomes** encoded in organization processes, documents, products, services, facilities and systems provided that the employees have the intention to share their what they know. In addition, other factors such as the **employee's skills** to articulate his/her knowledge and most importantly their awareness of the importance of sharing their know-**how and expertise and its effects on the organization's competitiveness** and productivity. These are fundamental keys of the knowledge creation culture in most organizations. Knowledge creation is integral, as knowledge is the only sustainable competitive advantage which is the result of learning. Furthermore, the creation and transmission of knowledge is seen as strategically significant as one of the fundamental processes that determine the ability of organizational learning and innovation (Salmador & Bueno, 2007). To answer the question of what is knowledge in an organization it can be said that it is all about action, focused innovation, pooled expertise, special relationships and alliances; also, it is value-added behavior and activities.

KM cycle involves both, creation or the acquisition of knowledge by an organization. Knowledge creation involves developing new knowledge or replacing existing knowledge with new content (Nonaka, 1994). Chen (2010) recognized two main categories of Knowledge: Explicit knowledge and Tacit knowledge. Explicit knowledge mainly refers to the structure knowledge expressed by text, images and symbols, which can be taught verbally and learned by textbooks, reference materials, databases, etc. Tacit knowledge only exists in people's minds, which is difficult to express by words, symbols, images media. The management of explicit knowledge is relatively easy; you can use information systems, such as code and database to set knowledge base. The explicit knowledge is achieved through teaching, training. The explicit knowledge is the basis for innovation. But the management of tacit knowledge is relatively more difficult. Tacit knowledge contains many knowledge cheats such as the work of know-how, experience, perspective and values, which implies more innovative ideas. These are the essence of the core Competitiveness. (Serban & Luan, 2002). Thus, knowledge management is the process of capturing, developing, sharing, and effectively using organizational knowledge.

Organizational knowledge is the interplay between two types of knowledge, Tacit and Explicit. Tacit knowledge is in people minds and is the result of past experiences, know-how, expertise etc and cannot be captured and shared easily. Explicit knowledge on the other hand is imbedded in the **organization's** processes, routines, books, images, symbols and can be easily made accessible and available to whomever is seeking specific knowledge. In this research we posit that in order to boost organizational competitiveness, tacit and explicit knowledge had key role by offering the organization a superior value proposition based on this knowledge. To create a knowledge sharing culture the organization needs to encourage people to work together more effectively, to collaborate and to share - ultimately to make organizational knowledge more productive (Gurteen, 1999).

2.2. KNOWLEDGE SHARING

The old paradigm was "knowledge is power" But today we posit that the real organizational power is in the sharing of what employees know and change the motto of organizations to the effective "sharing knowledge is power". The purpose of knowledge sharing is to help an organization as a whole to meet its

business objectives. If people understand that sharing their knowledge helps them do their jobs more effectively then knowledge sharing will become a reality (Gurteen, 1999).

Successful knowledge management applies a set of approaches to organizational knowledge—including its accumulation, utilization, sharing and ownership. Indeed, KM can be seen as a strategy that assists organizations to use knowledge to envisage, make and control the whole decision making process (Kong, 2009). Even with the low level of knowledge sharing that goes on today – if you do not make your knowledge productive than someone else with that same knowledge will. You can almost guarantee that whatever bright idea you have someone else somewhere in the organization will be thinking along the same lines. By sharing knowledge, there is possibility to gain more than lose. Sharing knowledge is a synergistic process. If I share a product idea or a way of doing things with another person – then just the act of putting my idea into words or writing will help me shape and improve that idea (Gurteen, 1999).

If people understand that sharing their knowledge helps them do their jobs more effectively; helps them retain their jobs; helps them in their personal development and career progression; and help the organization as a whole to be more productive and effective; rewards them for getting things done; and brings more personal recognition, then knowledge sharing will become a reality. Knowledge is perishable and is increasingly short-lived. If knowledge not shared, then it rapidly loses its value. Even with the low level of knowledge sharing that goes on today – if employees do not make their knowledge productive than someone else with that same knowledge will. By sharing knowledge, employees gain more than they lose. Sharing knowledge is a synergistic process – employees get more out than they put in. If one staff share a product idea or a way of doing things with another person – then just the act of putting my idea into words or writing will help him/her shape and improve that idea and improve Tacit & Explicit knowledge.

2.3. KM AND ORGANIZATIONAL COMPETENCY

Though described as a major business resource and a key source for attaining long-term CA (Gold et al., 2012), little evidence has been found of the direct effects of IT alone and performance correlations while at the same time, if existing (though not significant), frequent negative correlations suggest that IT may **worsen a firm's competitive position** (Powell and Dent-Micallef, 2011).

Organizational social resources generally comprise the sum of the actual and potential resources available that derive from the network of relationships possessed by a human or in a social unit (Nahapiet and Ghoshal, 2012). Lee and Choi (2003) propose that the ability of organizational structure, organizational culture, and people as the three critical dimensions of social KM resources to encourage the multifaceted activities associated with successful implementation of KM has been found to be a key distinguishing factor of successful firms. These valuable resources typically evolve over a long period of time through the accumulation of organizational operation experience (Gold et al., 2001), and thus, become hard to acquire and complex to duplicate. When effectively combined with the strong technical KM dimension they will become a unique organizational KM infrastructure capability which provides a sustained Competitive advantage (Chuang, 2014).

The value that knowledge management lies in increasing individual, team and organizational efficiency through the use of knowledge management tools (information technology). The higher the level of capturing knowledge (explicit or tacit) with information technology tools, the better the KM result (Lee & Choi, 2003).

Competency can be reached with the combination of precision and optimal use of manpower and material resources available and Efficiency is determined through performance. Efficiency and effectiveness are two important components of Competency and they are normally affected by different factors. But the Competency in organization is a series of coordinated and planned actions to improve the program and better use of talents, facilities, spaces and places. These practices design and implement in modern program (Tavari, 2008).

Most of the available studies relating to KM have considered organizational knowledge as a significant asset for gaining competitive advantage and as a significant contributor to the success and survival of any organization within a highly competitive business environment (Zack et al, 2009).

Akgün et al. (2006) argue that an urgent change in customer needs may initially lead design engineers to deny these changes are really needed and to refuse to alter original plans so as to avoid the additional stress. For organizational competitiveness to take place at the organizational level, some cultural barriers should be introduced in order to ensure that organizational members have adequate knowledge and **experience to perform their responsibilities (Hernández et al., 2010).** According to **Barney (1986) a firm's** culture, defined as a complex set of values, beliefs, assumptions, and symbols that define the way in which a firm conducts its business and can be a source of sustained competitiveness. According to the noted relations, research hypothesis is as below:

H1: Knowledge sharing effect Tacit knowledge of organization

H2: Knowledge sharing effect Explicit knowledge of organization

H3: Tacit knowledge effect knowledge management of organization

H4: Explicit knowledge effect knowledge management of organization

H5: Knowledge management effect Organizational competitiveness

Conceptual Model

2.4. METHODOLOGY

Sampling procedure of current research done among Saman insurance firm executives (in Tehran branches). Cochran sampling model was used for our sample community to make sure that we had proper size of samples, and considering Cochran formula with 0.05% level of error, and 95% assurance level, we **found out that the sample size shouldn't be less than 196.** The **credibility of the questionnaires** was tested by using the content credibility method. Beside it in order to calculate Cronbach alpha coefficient and determining the reliability of questionnaire, we have used SPSS software. The results demonstrated that alpha for the overall questionnaire was 0.87 which demonstrates high level of credibility.

2.5. DATA ANALYSIS RESULTS

It is very important to ensure the reliability and validity of research findings. This can be achieved by both emphasizing the adequacy of the research design and the quality of the measurement procedures employed. In order to validate the instruments, this study will perform validity and reliability tests. All the Reliability values of each construct are greater than the benchmark of 0.70 which recommended by Yin (2003) as good indicator of reliability.

Table 1. Assessment of reliability

Research construct	Number of Item	Reliability (Cronbach's alpha)
Knowledge sharing	5	0.85
Tacit knowledge	5	0.82
Explicit knowledge	5	0.90
Knowledge management	5	0.88
Organizational competitiveness	5	0.81

Source: Author

The analysis of this study show high significance of the theoretical foundation of **research’s variables, and** consequently all hypotheses were supported using Multiple Regression method. The results for the analysis of the variables analyze is shown in following table.

The results of all Hypothesis show that, all independent variables had significant positive impact on dependent variables so all hypothesis were supported (at the level of $p < 0.05$).

Table 2. Final Results of Hypothesis

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig	Result
	B	Std. Error	B			
Hypothesis 1	0.79	0.118	0.84	6.791	0.000	Supported
Hypothesis 2	0.85	0.076	0.93	11.260	0.000	Supported
Hypothesis 3	0.82	0.131	0.88	8.015	0.000	Supported
Hypothesis 4	0.90	0.153	0.91	6.455	0.000	Supported
Hypothesis 5	0.84	0.100	0.86	8.484	0.000	Supported

Source: Author

The results of first Hypothesis show that, Knowledge sharing had positive significant impact on Tacit knowledge of organization (B=0.84). Consequently, the hypothesis was supported

Results of second Hypothesis show that, Knowledge sharing had positive significant impact on Explicit knowledge of organization. (B=0.93). Consequently, the hypothesis was supported

Results of thirth Hypothesis show that, Tacit knowledge had positive significant impact on knowledge management of organization. (B=0.88). Consequently, the hypothesis was supported

Results of forth Hypothesis show that, Explicit knowledge had positive significant impact on knowledge management of organization. (B=0.91). Consequently, the hypothesis was supported

Results of firth Hypothesis show that, Knowledge management had positive significant impact on Organizational competiveness. (B=0.86). Consequently, the hypothesis was supported

3. CONCLUSIONS

This research intention was to investigate the existence of a positive impact of knowledge management on organizational competiveness. A survey study of 196 senior executives in the insurance industry provides strong support for the research model proposed. For this research, a new survey was developed and tested, and it proves to be a successful and justified new measure of knowledge management constructs in any organization. A direct result of this research is also a newly defined knowledge management model that consists of two empirically tested constructs (Tacit knowledge & Explicit). This model proves that the chosen constructs are a good measure for defining competiveness of organization. The results of this research also have several implications. First, the feedback from business practice supported the theoretical framework and hypotheses proposed in survey. The most important finding is that knowledge management components positively affect knowledge management of organizational which finally give firms better competiveness.

In terms of practical implications, the paper attempts to provide Iran's insurance firms executives, especially those from SMEs in the construction industry, with a better understanding about how firms need to be effectively managed to improve their overall KM infrastructure capability to leverage, exploit,

and sustain a Competiveness. In addition to consider a combination of tacit and explicit knowledge resource, managers should fascilitating sharing of knowledge through firms to overcome cultural barriers and strengthen their contribution to long-term performance.

Although many researchers have proposed different frameworks for assessing better productivity, this survey was conducted to identify and to understand components that play a role in a successful productivity which was competiveness. A major limitation of our work at the present stage is the absence of an empirical test. But understanding that the present work is the first and necessary step toward such a test, this limitation may be overlooked. It is our hope that when our model and proposed hypotheses are tested, the results would be very valuable to practitioners and academicians. More specifically, practitioners would be able to appreciate the effectiveness of various KM components, and be able to orientate their resources to those that are more beneficial to them in market.

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